

Infrared Spectra of Anthracene Sulphonates

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Infra-red spectra of anthracene and the sodium salts of anthracene-1-SO₃⁻ (1-ASO₃⁻), -2-SO₃⁻ (2-ASO₃⁻), -1, 5-diSO₃⁻ (1, 5 ASO₃⁻) and 1, 8-diSO₃⁻ (1, 8 ASO₃⁻) have been obtained in Nujol mull and in KBr pellets in the region 650-4000 cm⁻¹. Characteristic differences are observed in CH out of-plane deformation modes depending on the position of substitution of SO₃⁻ group in the anthracene skeleton. SO₃⁻ group frequencies 1000-1250 cm⁻¹ are also affected by the symmetry properties of the molecule. -C=C- skeletal modes which appear as progression in the absorption and emission spectra of these compounds in the region 1300 cm⁻¹ 1500 cm⁻¹ show interesting variations on substitution and may account for the variation of fluorescence spectra of these compounds in aqueous solutions. Presence of OH bonded water molecule is evident in disulphonates.

THE absorption and fluorescence spectra of anthracene show a vibrational progression of about 1400 cm⁻¹.

On substitution of SO₃⁻ group in the ring the absorption characteristics do not change to any large extent in aqueous solution. But the fluorescence spectra loses its vibrational structure and is red-shifted for 1- and 2- substituted anthracene sulphonates. The shift is largest for 1-ASO₃⁻. The 1 : 5- and 1 : 8-disubstituted compounds exhibit their normal vibrational progression. The emission spectra regains its vibrational structure on addition of solvents such as acetonitrile, EtOH, and ethylene glycol. The 1-ASO₃⁻ and 2-ASO₃⁻ differ from the disubstituted compounds in their other photochemical properties also, such as photodimerisation constant and quantum yield for fluorescence emission². These observations prompted us to look into the infrared spectra of these compounds, since C=E skeletal stretching modes and out of plane C-H bending modes have been implicated in radiationless deactivation of electronically excited aromatic hydrocarbons³.

Experimental

Anthracene 1-, 2-mono and 1:5- and 1 : 8-disodium sulphonates were prepared by reducing corresponding anthraquinones (B. D. H.) with Zn-dust and 20% NH₄OH for 4 to 6 hours. The products were treated with active animal charcoal to remove traces of anthraquinones and other impurities and recrystallized thrice from water.

The samples for infrared spectral studies at room-temperature were prepared either as solute in a drop of pure nujol or as KBr pellets. The mixture with pure and dry KBr was prepared by hand grinding in an agate mortar for 30 minutes. 5% concentration of anthracene sulphonates in KBr was used and the powder pressed under vacuum (8 tons/cm²) in a hydraulic press of the type ordinarily used in I. R. absorption spectroscopy.

I. R. spectra were recorded with Perkin-Elmer Infracord double beam spectrograph model 337.

Results

The infrared spectra of anthracene, sodium salts of anthracene-1-sulphonate (1-SO₃), anthracene 2-SO₃⁻ (2-SO₃⁻), anthracene-1, 5-disulphonate, (1, 5-diSO₃⁻) and anthracene-1, 8-disulphonate (1, 8-diSO₃⁻) in nujol mull are presented in Fig 1 and in KBr disc in Fig. 2. The spectra of nujol and of KBr disc are also incorporated in the respective figures for ready reference. The read-out of the spectra in wavenumber is tabulated in Tables 1 and 2 respectively for nujol and for KBr matrix.

Discussion

Although both in Nujol mull and KBr matrix, the sample exists in the solid state, in the latter dispersion is more uniform and a solid solution of the sample is obtained. In the Nujol mull the unit cell of the crystalline sample is maintained. Due to strong intermolecular forces within the rigid crystal environment of the solid, individual group vibrations are influenced by the nature of the unit cell. In suitable circumstances, in-phase and out-of-phase vibrations of the same groups in two different molecules may be set up leading to splitting of the original band into two. Nujol provides an environment of suitable refractive index so that scattering is minimised although intense Nujol absorption in the region of interest (~1460 cm⁻¹) is of great disadvantage. The KBr pellets are expected to be transparent throughout the region from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ but invariable presence of traces of water causes absorption at 3300 cm⁻¹. Furthermore in pressed alkali halide discs, spectral changes may occur due to degree of grinding. Polymorphism is also likely in highly polar crystalline molecules when under pressure. In finely dispersed samples, interactions may occur between vibrations of the sample and alkali halide

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Fig. 1. Infra-red spectra of anthracene and anthracene sulphonates sodium salt in nujol mull : (a) anthracene, (b) 1- SO_3^- , (c) 2- SO_3^- , (d) 1,5- SO_3^- (e) 1,8- SO_3^- and (f) nujol.

Fig 2 Infrared spectra of anthracene and anthracene sulphonates sodium salt in KBr pellets (a) anthracene, (b) 1-ASO₃⁻, (c) 2-SO₃⁻ (d) 1,5-SO₃⁻, (e) 1,8-SO₃⁻ and (f) KBr pellet

TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS IN NUJOL AS SODIUM SALT

Anthracene	A-1-SO ₃ ⁻	A-2-SO ₃ ⁻	A-1, 5-SO ₃ ⁻	A-1, 8-SO ₃ ⁻	
—	702 (s)	—	708 (s)	698 (m)	-SO ₃ ⁻ symmetric deformations
725 (vs)	727 (vs)	731 (vs)	724 (s)	740 (m)	
738 (m)	746 (w)	746 (sh)	—	—	3 adjacent H atom
746 (m)	793 (w)	—	787 (w)	775 (m)	2 adjacent H atom
—	810 (w)	—	791 (s)	792 (w)	
—	—	817 (w)	—	—	
—	839 (w)	—	847 (w)	—	9 : 10 position (out-of-plane)
883 (vs)	876 (s)	870 (w)	860 (s)	870 (w)	9, 10, position in-plane
890 (w)	893 (s)	—	873 (w)	—	
—	—	911 (s)	(broad)	—	
955 (s)	950 (w)	911 (s)	970 (w)	970 (vw)	
997 (m)	—	951 (m)	—	—	
—	1050 (vs) (asym)	1042 (s) (sym)	1045 (s)	1042 (vs) (broad)	-SO ₃ ⁻ Sym stretch
—	1118 (w)	1102 (s)	1060 (vs)	—	
1144 (m)	1132 (w)	1112 (s)	—	—	
1164 (w)	1162 (s)	—	1139 (m)	—	
—	1182 (vs)	1156 (m)	1160 (s)	1185 (vs) (broad)	SO ₃ ⁻ asym stretch
1271 (w)	—	1182 (vs)	1180 (s)	—	
1312 (w)	—	1233 (vs)	1210 (s)	—	
1612 (w)	—	—	—	—	
—	—	1293 (w)	1300 (w)	—	
—	—	—	1620 (m)	1600 (m)	H ₂ O (O—H bonded)
—	—	—	1340 (s)	3325 (s)	

TABLE 2—COMPOUND IN KBr DISC (5% w/w) AS SODIUM SALT

Anthracene	A-1-SO ₃ ⁻	A-2-SO ₃ ⁻	A-1,5-SO ₃ ⁻	A-1,8-SO ₃ ⁻
—	704 (vs)	—	708 (vs)	702 (m)
725 (s)	727 (vs)	728 (vs)	727 (s)	—
737 (s)	—	733 (vs)	—	738 (m)
743 (s)	747 (s)	742 (s)	—	—
—	778 (m)	770 (w)	—	774 (m)
—	793 (m)	804 (w)	794 (3)	797 (w)
—	—	813 (m)	—	814 (vw)
—	840 (m)	846 (w)	848 (sh, m)	—
884 (s)	876 (vs)	872 (s)	862 (s)	870 (w)
—	—	876 (s)	878 (sh, m)	—
898 (m)	—	—	894 (vw)	893 (vw)
905 (s)	913 (w)	914 (s)	—	—
—	924 (w)	—	923 (w)	—
955 (s)	950 (m)	940 (m)	—	932 (w)
—	—	953 (m)	—	—
976 (w)	973 (m)	982 (w)	966 (m)	970 (w)
996 (s)	1005 (m)	1000 (m)	—	—
—	1050 (vs)	1028 (m)	—	1035 (s)
—	—	1045 (s)	1050 (vs)	1055 (s)
—	1120 (s)	1103 (s)	broad	1065 (s)
—	—	1116 (s)	—	—
1140 (m)	1136 (s)	—	1140 (vs)	—
1166 (w)	1167 (s)	—	—	—
—	1184 (vs)	1186 (vs)	—	1171 (s)
—	1205	1240 (s)	—	broad
—	—	—	1210 (vs)	(broad)
1266 (w)	1275 (m)	1267 (s)	(1110-1250)	—
1308 (m)	1312 (m)	1300 (m)	—	1322 (w)
—	1337 (w)	1330 (w)	1310 (m)	1348 (w)
1440 (m)	1420 (m)	1445 (m)	1342 (m)	1425 (m)
—	1450 (w)	1448 (m)	1400 (m)	1450 (m)
—	1531 (m)	1525 (m)	—	—
—	3000	3000 (s)	1525 (w)	—
—	3120	3120 (s)	3020	—
—	3400 (s)	3380 (s)	3420 (vs)	3400 (s)

lattice. Therefore spectra may show differences from those examined in paraffin oil.

The infra-red spectrum of anthracene consists of prominent absorption bands between 900 and 500 cm⁻¹ which are associated with out-of-plane C-H bending vibrations. The spectra of anthracene sulphonate sodium salt, show characteristic differences in the 1000-650 cm⁻¹ region. The symmetry of the molecule changes on the position and number of substituents in the anthracene ring. The 1-and 2-substituted compounds are totally asymmetric and fall in the point group C_{2v}. The 1,5-substituted compound belongs to the point group symmetry species C_{2v} whereas 1,8-substituted compound to C_{2v}. Furthermore 1-SO₃⁻ has 3

vicinal or adjacent H-atoms on the substituted ring and 4 on the unsubstituted ring; 2-SO₃⁻ has 1 and 2 vicinal H-atoms in the substituted ring and 4 in the unsubstituted ring; 1,5-diSO₃⁻ and 1,8-diSO₃⁻ have 3 vicinal H atoms on both the rings. All the four compounds have 9, 10 positions unsubstituted. The differences in the spectra in this region of out-of-plane CH deformation vibration mode have to be looked into with these perspective.

The unsubstituted anthracene shows a strong band at 725 cm⁻¹ with two satellites of decreasing intensity at the higher frequency side at 737 cm⁻¹ and 746 cm⁻¹. The nature of the spectrum changes characteristically on substitution of -SO₃⁻ group. A strong band appear

at 702 cm^{-1} , 708 cm^{-1} and 698 cm^{-1} in 1-SO_3^- , $1,5\text{-diSO}_3^-$ and $1,8\text{-diSO}_3^-$ although it is conspicuously missing in 2-SO_3^- . The strong band in this region, in sulphones and sulphonic acids is normally ascribed to $\nu(\text{CS})$ symmetric stretching vibrations⁴ or to $-\text{SO}_3^-$ group vibration⁵ but its absence in 2-SO_3^- casts some doubt on this simple explanation. In disubstituted compounds, this band appears to have a high frequency partner of equal intensity at 724 cm^{-1} in $1,5\text{-SO}_3^-$ and at 740 cm^{-1} in $1,8\text{-SO}_3^-$ ($\Delta\bar{\nu}=16\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 42 cm^{-1} respectively). In KBr disc these bands are at 704 cm^{-1} , 708 cm^{-1} and 702 cm^{-1} respectively for 1-, 1,5- and 1,8-substituted compounds. Its absence in 2-SO_3^- suggests that perhaps it arises due to interaction of bulky $-\text{SO}_3^-$ group with the peri hydrogen which may give rise to weak bonding interaction of the type $-\text{C}-\text{H} \cdots \text{O}-\text{SO}_3^-$. In that case the intensity should increase in the disubstituted compounds. The second explanation is that perhaps it is due to parallel type symmetric deformation mode of $-\text{SO}_3^-$ which is perpendicular to the long axis of the ring. A parallel type symmetric deformation mode appears at 624 cm^{-1} for $-\text{ClO}_3^-$ ion⁶ which has a geometry similar to $-\text{SO}_3^-$. Such an assignment will explain the splitting of the band in disubstituted compounds. In $1,8\text{-(SO}_3^-)$ steric effect between the two $-\text{SO}_3^-$ may cause distortion of the ring and lowering of the intensity.

The strong band at 725 cm^{-1} region in anthracene has been assigned by Cannon and Sutherland⁷ to 4 adjacent H atoms in aromatic ring. This band appears at 721 cm^{-1} in 1-SO_3^- with a weak satellite at 746 cm^{-1} and in 2-SO_3^- at 731 cm^{-1} and a shoulder at 746 cm^{-1} . Interesting differences between 2-SO_3^- and others are also observed in the region of bands for three adjacent H-atoms near 800 cm^{-1} . 1-SO_3^- gives a weak band at 793 cm^{-1} which is absent in anthracene as well as in 2-SO_3^- compound but appears with considerable intensity at 787 cm^{-1} (w), 791 cm^{-1} (m) in $1,5\text{-SO}_3^-$ and 775 cm^{-1} (m), 792 cm^{-1} (w) for $1,8\text{-SO}_3^-$. The alteration in intensity of two closely spaced bands in the disubstituted compounds appears to be related to their symmetry properties. A small split peak at 817 cm^{-1} assigned to two vicinal H-atoms appears in 2-SO_3^- and is absent in others. A weak band also appears at 839 cm^{-1} in 1-SO_3^- and at 847 cm^{-1} in $1,5\text{-SO}_3^-$ which is absent in anthracene. In KBr matrix all these bands become much more prominent and minor shifts in their frequencies occur.

The band at 883 cm^{-1} is the second strongest band in unsubstituted anthracene and has a weak but well resolved partner at 890 cm^{-1} . Canon & Sutherland⁷ have suggested that band in this region arises from C-H bonds approximately perpendicular to the long axis of the molecule and Thompson et al⁸ explain it as due to C-H vibrations at 3 and 4 positions. The band persists in 1-SO_3^- at 876 cm^{-1} (s) but in 2-SO_3^- three bands of equal intensity appear at 870 cm^{-1} , 893 cm^{-1} and 911 cm^{-1} . In $1,5\text{-SO}_3^-$ the band structure is modified, 860 cm^{-1} (s) and 873 cm^{-1} (w) and in $1,8\text{-SO}_3^-$ only one broad and weak band appear at 870 cm^{-1} . The characteristic variation for 2-SO_3^- is striking. In KBr matrix these bands become more prominent and well defined. Next important band in this region appear at

955 cm^{-1} in anthracene and is likely to be due to isolated H atom at 9 and 10 position of the ring. The band is weak in 1-SO_3^- but gains in intensity for 2SO_3^- . In disubstituted compounds it is shifted to high frequency region and appears weakly in $1,5\text{SO}_3^-$ but is nearly non-existent in $1,8\text{SO}_3^-$. This behaviour is as expected because bulky $-\text{SO}_3^-$ is likely to interact with peri-hydrogen and steric effect in $1,8\text{-substituted}$ compound may be so large as to cause distortion of the ring. The repulsive interaction between two negatively charged groups in juxtaposition may enhance the same effect.

The region between 950 cm^{-1} and 1200 cm^{-1} which is the region for characteristic vibrations of C-H in-plane-deformation modes in aromatic hydrocarbons are superimposed by strong vibrational frequencies of the $-\text{SO}_3^-$ group in these anthracene sulphonates. The small spike of medium intensity observed at 998 cm^{-1} in anthracene is not observed in the substituted compounds.

The next region between $1000\text{-}1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is mainly associated with $-\text{SO}_3^-$ group vibrations. The unsubstituted anthracene has a medium intensity band at 1144 cm^{-1} with a weak partner at 1164 cm^{-1} . According to Colthup⁹ as quoted by Bellamy⁵ sulfonic acids and their salts absorb in three ranges $1260\text{-}1150\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1080\text{-}1010\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $700\text{-}600\text{ cm}^{-1}$. From infrared spectra of dipolar isomeric amine sulphonic acids in CS_2 solution, Ganguly, Jose & Biswas¹⁰ ascribe two strong bands at $1029\text{-}1044\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1150\text{-}1230\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to symmetric and asymmetric stretching modes of SO_3^- group, the latter bond being usually split and broad. The splitting of ν_{as} ($-\text{SO}_3^-$) is also reported by Evans¹¹ from his studies on *m*- and *p*-aminobenzene sulphonic acids and their salts. In the present study of anthracene sulphonate sodium salt, pattern of bands show considerable variations in this region for 1-, 2-, 1,5- and 1,8-compounds. The strong band at 1050 cm^{-1} in 1-SO_3^- has slight asymmetry on the high frequency side indicating a tendency to split but the same band in 2-SO_3^- appear at 1040 cm^{-1} with reduced intensity and is fairly symmetrical. On the other hand in disubstituted compounds, definite doublet appears, peaking at 1045 cm^{-1} and 1060 cm^{-1} for $1,5\text{-SO}_3^-$ which becomes a strong broad band at 1042 cm^{-1} for $1,8\text{-SO}_3^-$. The splitting of this band in 1-, 1,5- and 1,8-substituted compounds may again be due to parallel mode of this stretching vibration and interaction between the substituents along the short axis of the molecule. The absorption between $1140\text{-}1270\text{ cm}^{-1}$, show one broad and intense band in $1,8\text{-SO}_3^-$ and fine structure which differ for each compound in the other three sulphonates. The bands in 2-SO_3^- are more resolved with doublet at $1102\text{-}1112\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of fair intensity and two strong bands at 1182 cm^{-1} . A medium intensity line also appears at 1156 cm^{-1} , which has counterparts in unsubstituted anthracene at 1144 cm^{-1} (w) and 1164 cm^{-1} (w). In KBr pellets, weak but sharp peaks appear at 1140 cm^{-1} (m), 1166 cm^{-1} (w), 1266 cm^{-1} (w) in anthracene. For aromatic hydrocarbons, the frequencies in this region are assigned to C-H in-plane deformation modes and have been used for characterisation of substitution pattern⁶. For other three com-

pounds the range is narrowed down slightly and the four peaks overlap. The values are: 1-SO₃⁻: 1118 cm⁻¹(w), 1132 cm⁻¹(w), 1162 cm⁻¹(s) and 1182 cm⁻¹(v.s.); 1,5 -SO₃⁻: 1139 cm⁻¹(m), 1160 cm⁻¹(s), 1180 cm⁻¹(s) and 1210 (v. s.); 1,8 -SO₃⁻: 1185 cm⁻¹(v.s. and broad). The asymmetric stretching mode of -SO₃⁻ is known to be split and the split is smaller in the Na-salt¹¹. In these series of compounds, only 2-SO₃⁻ show a splitting of 30 cm⁻¹ whereas in other cases it is much smaller. It appears that this perpendicular type asymmetric vibration interacts more strongly in the direction of long axis of the molecule, or SO₃⁻ frequency is influenced by CH frequencies due to steric reasons. The substitution in 1- and 2- positions may change the type of unit cell obtained in the crystal lattice of the solids. This may be the reason that the absorption pattern shows considerable change in nujol mull and in KBr pellets,

The region between 2000 cm⁻¹ to 1250 cm⁻¹ do not give much information because of the absorption by nujol itself. Besides nujol bands, there is a weak band at 1312 cm⁻¹ and another one at 1612 cm⁻¹ which are characteristic for the aromatic ring multiple stretching modes. The 1612 cm⁻¹ band which appears weakly in anthracene is prominent and broad in disubstituted compounds. It is nearly non-existent in monosubstituted derivatives. The characteristic skeletal in-plane vibrational modes are observable in KBr pellets since KBr is supposed to be transparent in this region. A medium intensity at 1308 cm⁻¹ and another at 1440 cm⁻¹ is observed in anthracene. In substituted compounds many more bands appear in this region ranging from 1275 cm⁻¹ to 1620 cm⁻¹. The KBr disc itself shows a broad band 1450-1660 cm⁻¹ which may be due to some impurity. The band at 1308 cm⁻¹ is split in the substituted compounds. So is the band at 1440 cm⁻¹ except for 1,5 -SO₃⁻ for which it appears at 1400 cm⁻¹. These skeletal modes are observed as vibrational progression in absorption and emission spectra. Therefore it is interesting to note that the emission spectra of 1,5- and 1,8-disulphonates in aqueous solutions have vibrational structure whereas those for 1-SO₃⁻ is structureless and 2-SO₃⁻ has only weak structure. Furthermore the CH deformation modes and -C=C, skeletal stretching mode are involved in the mechanism of radiationless transitions as postulated by Siebrand⁸ and influence the fluorescence yields of these compounds. 1 -SO₃⁻, 2 -SO₃⁻ and 1,5 -SO₃⁻ give bands at 1531 cm⁻¹(s), 1525 cm⁻¹(w) and 1525 cm⁻¹(w) respectively in KBr pellets. A strong band at 1620 cm⁻¹ occurs only for the disubstituted compounds in nujol

mull. The activation of many more vibrational modes in KBr matrices suggests that these modes are very sensitive to environmental perturbations and may account for the solvent effect on the emission spectra of these compounds.

Within the range 3500 cm⁻¹ to 2000 cm⁻¹ there is not much structure observable in nujol mull for all the compounds except for a strong band at 3410 cm⁻¹ for 1,5 -SO₃⁻ and 3325 cm⁻¹ for 1,8 -SO₃⁻ on the high frequency side of nujol peak. These are definitely due to hydrogen bonded OH groups since these disubstituted compounds contain 2 and 3 moles of water of crystallisation respectively¹². In KBr matrix peaks appear at 3000 cm⁻¹ and 3120 cm⁻¹ for monosubstituted derivatives which is not clearly defined in disubstituted ones. The latter again show strong band at 3420 cm⁻¹ due to presence of water molecules. The KBr peak appears strongly at 3333 cm⁻¹. A complete analysis of the spectra has not been possible for such a complex molecule.

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